

The Styles of the Artists Creating in the Landscape Genre Analysis

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Abstract:

This article talks about the attention given to the field of art, the analysis of the styles of the artists who created in the landscape genre, and the feeling of the image with the whole body, leaving an indelible mark on the field of visual art of our country.

Keywords: Fine art, still life, color gloss, art and culture, Arol Tansikbayev, constructive construction, working in color.

Art and culture in Uzbekistan have been developing since ancient times and have their own history. Especially in recent years, the increased attention paid to the field of art has made creative hearts even more happy. Art and culture have enriched our heritage at various stages over the centuries. Today, with the initiatives of our proud president Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich, there are incomparable opportunities for today's young people to rise to higher levels in the world of art. For this, our youth must know and appreciate the work of our compatriots who made a great contribution to this field. Miniatures are considered the oldest works of visual art in Central Asia, and the flourishing of this art dates back to the 15th century. Kamoliddin Behzod was a guiding star that led creativity in this direction. The unique miniaturist artist made portraits of his contemporaries: Sultan Husayn Baigaro, Shaibani Khan, poets Jami, Khatifi, and left his signature indelibly in the history. Kamoliddin Behzod painted his portraits often with solid colors. This miniaturist artist closely observed all life in existence and created works based on his imagination following certain rules of composition. As we know, the cultural heritage and traditions of the peoples of Central Asia are diverse. However, they did not find a real reflection in the field of visual arts. Since 1960, Arol Tansikbayev created realistic and unique works in the landscape genre, and laid the foundation for the flourishing development of this genre. The artist's works were not only in the gold fund of the Art Museum of Uzbekistan, but also in famous museums in the world. These

works: Issyk kol, Ona olka, Kuzkabi in the morning are preserved in the gallery of Fredyakov. The work of Rakhim Akhmedov, a passionate and ambitious artist who contributed to the development and prosperity of the visual art of Uzbekistan, is incomparable. The months before the artist, Dawn, Sora Akhmedova, a woman from Surkhandarya. Rakhim Akhmedov was able to create a unique look in the field of portraiture. Through the images of women, old people and young people, he tried to reveal not only the external but also the human qualities of their faces. Painting is not only a type of visual art, but also the basis and guarantee of artistic skill for all types of visual art. The possibilities of expressing ideas through the gloss of colors have expanded. An artist should analyze and express the beauty and charm of being. Otherwise, the image will look lifeless. The fine art schools listed above managed to achieve the level of popularity through their few skills. They felt the image with their whole body, inherited the works in their true sense, and left an indelible mark on the field of visual arts of our country. The task of us young people is to carefully analyze and preserve this work. Because, after this legacy, the field of visual arts will rise and achieve higher results without a doubt. Landscape is one of the oldest genres of fine art and plays an important role as a background in historical domestic and still life works.

In landscape works, a person's personality, intelligence, and inner feelings are described through images and they create an image of nature. The works of the landscape genre in fine art form the love of nature and beauty qualities in a person. In the work of the artists, we can see that they refer directly to the landscape in the works on historical, domestic and still-life themes. In this view, of course, the landscape genre plays the role of background. In Europe, the landscape genre began to develop in the XVI-XVII centuries. And in the Netherlands, artists managed to soften the appearance of nature and depict it in its original state. In Russia, the development of this genre dates back to the 18th century. This genre reflects the beauty of the outside world and has a positive effect on the human mind. For this reason, artists teach to feel the most delicate, typical situations of the natural world, color harmonies, and aesthetic relations to nature with their works. For example, I. Levitan's Literary Silence, I. Shishkin's "Forest Distances" and B. Meskov's works about the Urals. The republican art exhibitions organized after the era of the revolution began to show a positive impact on the development of visual art in Uzbekistan. Artists began to interpret Mother Nature in a special way. He did not depict urban, industrial and lyrical scenes, but his interest in nature continued to grow. With this interest and enthusiasm, Arol Tansikbayev took the lead in the development of the landscape genre in Uzbekistan in the 50s of the 20th century. The artist created works on the theme of agriculture. For example, we can take the spring in Uzbekistan in 1950, the centuries of cotton irrigation. The gentle breeze blowing in the early morning, the trickling water is an impressive tool that evokes the cool and soft nature. The Motherland, created in 1951, reflects the objective laws of life and the epic state of revolutionary development. Solving the composition solution in a panoramic way became one of the characteristic points of this artist's work. In 1957, the dawn of Qairaqum HPP was recognized as the best industrial landscape work. Looking at this work, we can see the panorama of the construction of a large hydroelectric power station, the slightly colored Qairakum sea in the background, the unfinished hill, bulldozer cranes on the dam, sandy dunes in the foreground, and the old man behind the dam. It is an important factor not only to observe the work of the landscape painters of Uzbekistan, but also to observe the works of European and Russian artists, analyze their unique methods as an example in the training process, and use them as an exhibition. Of course, the hard work of the artist lies in the creation of high-quality works. It depends on the skill of the visual arts teacher to be able to show the results of this hard work and increase the interest of students. It is clear that a teacher of fine arts, who approaches his profession wholeheartedly and uses all his skills, will achieve the goal he set for himself. Fine art technology and copying science are the basis of all specialist subjects taught in art faculties and provide the connection between them. Without acquiring sufficient knowledge and skills in technology, a student cannot master composition, pencil drawing, painting, sculpture, folk art and

other subjects at a high level. Currently, the development of the theoretical and methodological bases of training in art faculties of pedagogic universities and the development of a new scientifically based way, form, content, and methods of specialized subjects, fine art technology and photocopying, are among the most urgent problems. They are as follows: to determine the current state of teaching art technology and copy science classes and to develop its future prospective ways;

The visual art of Uzbekistan is the creation of folk artists, folk masters, the materials of ancient sculpture art, to teach young people to learn and aesthetic education to read visual art works, to analyze the science of visual art technology from a scientific and methodological point of view. Every artist in his works If it sets immortal ideas as its main goal and can express them skillfully, then literature, culture and art literally serve spiritual growth. On this basis, the formation of the necessary theoretical and educational-methodological base for the education of young artists will undoubtedly allow to carry out practical work on the training of specialists who meet today's requirements and to solve these problems.

Nowadays, the field of visual arts requires a lot of knowledge and skill from the artist. It can be seen that there are many trends in contemporary art. At the same time, this module is also about pencil drawing, which is the main foundation of fine art. In this manual, the types of pencil drawing, ways to learn it, the use of perspective in pencil drawing, composition (placing on paper), proportion (dimensions), constructive construction, working with color, working with lines. , pencil drawing technologies, paper, pencil, charcoal, saucina, working with retouches, working on details, etc. will give general concepts. Innovation, an important part of large-scale reforms, is showing its advantages in the education system today, as in every field. Currently, the concept of "innovation" is very widely used. The word "innovation" is an English word that means "innovation", i.e. it is defined as changing the internal structure of the system. Innovation is an important part of practice and theory, and it is a system of action of social subjects aimed at improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object. Innovations are relevant, important, new approaches formed in a system. They are born on the basis of initiatives and innovations, and are promising for the development of educational content. It also has a positive effect on the development of the education system as a whole. During these periods, the worldview of artists, the socio-historical, national and methodological features of nature perception are little expressed in the depiction of natural landscapes. Accordingly, in the works of famous artists, one can find magnificent romantic (F. Vasiliev), lyrical (A. Sovrasov) or socio-philosophical (I. Leviton) interpretations of landscape motifs.

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